

Three rice varieties – IR20, IR36, and Dular – were grown in both types of units. ET data were collected from the 2 units from 15 days after planting until flowering. There was good agreement of data obtained from each type of unit. When graphed, the distribution of data points along a 1:1 line indicated that both microlysimeters are reliable and accurate for ET measurement in wetland rice fields.

The table shows an example of ET rates for the 3 cultivars and pan

Evapotranspiration rate at maximum tillering growth stage on 1 clear day for 3 cultivars of rice grown at IRRI in the 1978 dry and wet seasons.

Date	Season	Evapotranspiration (mm/day)			Av pan evaporation (mm/day)	Solar radiation (cal/cm ² per day)
		IR36	IR20	Dular		
13 Apr	Dry	10.0	9.0	8.2	8.8	663
25 Sep	Wet	5.7	4.3	7.8	4.8	571
19 Dec	Wet	4.2	4.3	6.2	4.2	476

evaporation and solar radiation values on 3 clear days at about the maximum tillering stage in the 1978 dry and wet seasons.

Simple to fabricate and maintain the

microlysimeters can be made locally and handled easily. The microlysimeter principle might also be applied to ecological studies of water use by non-crop aquatic and semi-aquatic species. ■

Soil and crop management

Role of balanced fertilizers in increasing farmers' rice yields and profits

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To examine the potential of using recommended levels of balanced fertilizers, an experiment was conducted in a farmer's field at the BRRI cropping systems research site at Laskarchala in 1979 aus. The variety Chandina (BR1)

was used; the crop was transplanted, with supplemental irrigation. The experiment was in a randomized complete block design with four replications.

Treatments consisted of 4 levels of fertilizer application: the farmer's level (26-47-0 kg N-P₂O₅-K₂O/ha), the recommended level for N + the farmers' level of P₂O₅ (80-47-0 kg N-P₂O₅-K₂O/ha), the recommended level for N-P₂O₅-K₂O (80-60-40 kg/ha), and the recommended level for N-P₂O₅-K₂O plus sulfur as SO₄ (80-60-40-34 kg/ha).

The yield was highest from the recommended level for NPK plus sulfur (4.3 t/ha), but it did not differ significantly from the treatment without sulfur (3.9 t/ha) (see table).

Replacing the farmer's level of N only with the recommended level significantly increased grain yield (3.3 t/ha vs 2.6 t/ha). Economic analysis of the extra costs and returns over the farmer's level indicated that investing an extra US\$16.57–31.53/ha could bring an extra net return of US\$129.00–372.28/ha. ■

Agroeconomic evaluation of extra nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and sulfur over the farmer's level of management in the 1979 aus at the Laskarchala BRRI Cropping Systems Research Site.

Treatment	Fertilizer rate (kg/ha)				Yield ^a (t/ha)	Added yield over farmer's level (t/ha)	Value of added yield (US\$/ha)	Cost of added inputs (US\$/ha)	Added profit over farmer's level (US\$/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
	N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	SO ₄						
1 ^b	26	47	0	0	2.6 c	–	–	–	–	–
2	80	47	0	0	3.3 b	0.6	145.58	16.57	129.01	7.7
3 ^c	80	60	40	0	3.9 a	1.3	308.51	26.63	281.88	10.5
4	80	60	40	34	4.3 a	1.7	403.80	31.53	372.28	11.8

^aCV = 6%. Mean yields with a common letter did not differ significantly at the 1% level. ^bFarmer's level. ^cRecommended level.

Varietal reaction of rice to age of seedlings transplanted in alkali soil

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An experiment conducted on an alkali soil (pH 8.2, ESP: 15.47%, and EC: 0.48 mmho/cm at 25°C) in 1977–78 kharif studied the effects of transplanting

seedlings of different ages. The split-plot design had varieties in the main plot and seedling age in the subplot. Fertilizer was applied at 120 kg N/ha (60 kg basal, 30 kg 20 days after transplanting [DT], and 30 kg at 40 DT irrespective of growth stage), 60 kg P₂O₅/ha, and 80 kg K₂O/ha as basal. Three healthy seedlings were transplanted in each hill.

The table shows that the period

required for establishment was not greatly influenced by the age of seedlings at transplanting. However, seedlings older than 25 days were established 1 or 2 days earlier. The time from panicle emergence to maturity generally was shorter in the short-duration variety Bala than in the medium-duration Ratna and the long-duration Sona. But in all three varieties, the time was shorter in seedlings